

Engineering perspective of Melamchi disaster and Mitigation Methods

Ishwar Joshi¹, Rakesh Kumar Chaudhary², Diwakar K C³

¹Project Engineer, Hydro Lab. Lalitpur, Nepal. E-mail: ij@hydrolab.org

²Water Resource Development, Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Roorke

E-mail: logtokumarrakesh063@gmail.com

³Graduate Research Assistant, Dept. of Civil and Environmental Engineering, University of Toledo, Toledo, OH 43606, USA. E-mail: Diwakar.KC@rockets.utoledo.edu

Introduction and Background

Nepal, with 80 percent of its area comprising fragile Himalayan mountain system, has been facing a number of disasters since of late (Yamaba and Sharma, 1993; Dhital, 2003; Dahal, 2006; Bhandary et al., 2013; Dahal and Dahal, 2017; Dangi et al., 2019, K C et al., 2021). Loss of property and destruction of riverine infrastructures are in increasing order due to landslide flood and debris flows.

The country drains around 6000 rivers and rivulets from North to South. It receives more than 80% of annual precipitation within the period of about four months (June to September). This leads to heavy floods each year. Furthermore, climate change has increased average temperature by 0.104 degree centigrade per decade in Hindu Kush Himalayan region (Ren et al., 2017). This increases the glacier ice melting loading the flow to the river systems. Correspondingly, additional flow from Glacier Lake Outburst Flood (GLOF) and permafrost melting generate high discharge with rapid flow resulting in excess stream power leading to morphological extremes with high bed and bank erosion, sediment transport, and granular flows. Under such a circumstance, development activities within rivers and in its vicinity will be more challenging, especially for a developing country like Nepal, India, Bhutan, and Pakistan.

The wide accepted rule in water resources engineering while developing infrastructures above or within a river is a concept of high flood. High flood concept is based on probability and risk estimate. The engineers and scientists use the concept of high flood while planning residential areas, design bridges, hydropower projects, culverts, highways, flood walls; yet, the impact of sediment load and debris flows during design is generally ignored that could be critical for the dynamic river basins. During debris flow with the same amount of water discharge the flow depth and total discharge increases due to presence of debris load in the flow. The increased flow significantly crossing the historical high flood level. The increased flow depth and total discharge can easily overtop the previous high flood level thereby flooding the surrounding areas and depositing the debris materials.

Melamchi Disaster

A recent debris flow and sediment disaster in Melamchi on June 15, 2021 was a fatal example, that killed many people, destroyed human settlements and infrastructures of national importance. A large area of land was eroded along with the deposition of debris in Melamchi town and along the Melamchi riverbed causing loss of property having value of millions of dollars. The difference before and after the June 15, 2021 event at Melamchi town can be seen in Figure 1. The debris flow also damaged the headworks of Melamchi Water Supply Project - a critical project that supplies water for 2.5 million people in Capital city-Kathmandu. Likewise, most of the river crossing structures, for instance bridges in Melamchi River have experienced heavy sediment loading with notable decrease in vertical clearance (Figure 2 left). The impact of decrease in vertical clearance can be immediate and cause the flow to overtop the bridge even in normal flow and in flood events the bridges can be washed away.

Figure 1: Melamchi town before the debris flow event (left) and after the debris flow event (right)

The flooding in Melamchi was not just due to increased water discharge as the rainfall measured in the catchment was well below the monsoon average but most likely it was due to the formation of temporary landslide dam that blocked the river which subsequently breached leading to the propagation of large flood wave and debris flow downstream. Had the human settlements not been extended to lower alluvial deposits, around the bend in Figure 2 (left), the fatalities and property loss could have been minimized.

Figure 2: Closer view of debris deposited at Melamchi town (left), Motorable Bridge across Indrawati river at Dolalghat in Arniko Highway (Source: Image posted by Nepal Flying Labs and Kantipur newsportal)

Challenges and Suggestions

Until now there is no concrete plan and practice to tackle the possible Landslide Dam Outburst Flood (LDOF). Some technical strategy should be initiated to cope with the debris flows mobilized from the sudden breach of landslide dams. The Gorkha Earthquake in 2015 has caused many minor cracks in the surrounding mountains. The cracks when filled with rainwater in monsoon can trigger many landslides; therefore, identification of such potential landslide prone areas and risk assessment is necessary to manage geomorphological catastrophe. This can also help in to plan and locate new settlement areas. Of course, the settlement areas should be well above the highest flood level but still there should be consideration of debris flow as the flow depth is significantly high during debris flows even when the water discharge or rainfall intensity is modest. More research on debris/mud flow is necessary. The possible runout distance and flow depth and deposition height of affected area can be estimated by debris/mudflow routing or by proper numerical simulations (K C et al., 2021).

Similarly, adequate river management system is necessary. The prevalent river management system in Nepal is traditional and it is somehow outdated. Methodology and techniques developed decades back are found to apply in all the hydropower, water supply, irrigation projects or in design of bridges or culverts. Therefore, it is necessary to study the long and short-term impacts on natural process of a river, that help to mitigate disasters. In recent years, nature-based solution is getting attention in river engineering since it doesn't disturb natural processes of river system though it fulfills the need. Hence, such new methods can be incorporated to improve the river management system.

Residential area planning based on floodplain zoning with due consideration of geomorphological hazards is essential. It has already become crucial to carry out a thorough research before infrastructure development and planning settlement areas that sustain the environment. The central government as well as local government should have well defined executable strategy considering hazards and risk like landslide mobilized debris flows or landslide dam breached flash floods on state-of-the-art knowledge and technology. Real time flood forecasting system, remote sensing technology, computer-based modeling system, database management can be helpful for the reduction of probable hazards. For instance, remote sensing technology like high-resolution multi-spectral satellite imagery, LIDAR, or Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) can be used for monitoring mountainous catchment to detect incipient hill slope failures, glaciers, ice mass as well as detachment of well entrenched permafrost.

Disasters like Melamchi flood can be prevented only by thorough research and well-planned development. It is necessary for the government to establish research centers for disaster prevention, mitigation, and rehabilitation of hydraulic infrastructures. The government bodies at different levels can cooperate and coordinate with such research centers to understand the physical process of the river system and estimate hazard and risk resulting disasters that can be a backbone to save lives and property.

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